

Abstracts of the series of presentations, Lincoln, New Zealand. 2015.

Fungi in changing ecosystems: Ian Dickie [Lincoln University]

**Extending the vertical perspective on Earth's skin – soils within the Critical Zone framework:
Andre Eger [Landcare Research]**

Ericoid root symbioses and soil carbon cycling: Gwen Grelet [Landcare Research]

Mobilisation of selenium on the South Island West Coast: David Hawke [CPIT]

Options to reduce nitrate leaching losses from agricultural soils: Brendon Malcolm [Plant & Food Research]

Evaluating soil oxygen as determining factor in nitrous oxide emissions: Jen Owens [AGLS Lincoln University]

Earthworm contribution to ecosystem services: Nicole Schon [AgResearch]

Supporting sustainable intensification of the New Zealand forestry industry: Simeon Smaill [SCION]

Soils: a key reservoir of life on Earth - what we know and don't know: Steve Wakelin [AgResearch]

Soil acidity and aluminium toxicity in New Zealand soils: Amy Whitley [Lincoln University]

Fungi in changing ecosystems: Ian Dickie [Lincoln University]

Fungi form a diverse and critical part of soil ecosystems, yet the response of fungal communities to changing ecosystems remain largely unknown. Based recent results, there are an estimated 41 000 species of fungi native to New Zealand, with perhaps an additional 27 000 introduced species. These fungi form critical links between above and belowground (soil) ecosystems, including the role of mycorrhizal fungi in plant nutrient uptake, the role of soil borne pathogens in driving plant mortality and hence community composition, and the role of saprotrophic fungi in returning plant nutrients to the soil. Fungal communities are, however, sensitive to both natural and anthropogenic change, including soil development, changing plant communities, and land-use intensification. I will present three vignettes linking fungal communities to major gradients of ecosystem change. First, I present the response of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi and oomycete communities to 120 000 years of soil development at Franz Josef. Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungal communities show strong evidence of niche partitioning by fungi for different ecosystem stages, with host-plant associations, not pedogenesis, being the most proximate driver. Using a network analysis approach, we find no change in plant-fungal interaction network nestedness, but that network position (centrality) is an important predictor of how novel network linkages form. Oomycete communities also show significant differentiation with site age, playing a particularly important role in the early stages of ecosystem development, but only a minor role in older ecosystems. Second, I continue the theme of linked plant- and fungal communities by examining how the widespread introduction of exotic plants into New Zealand has influenced ectomycorrhizal fungal communities. In particular, we find that most fungi associated with exotic trees are also exotic. Taking a network analysis approach suggests these plant-fungal co-introductions are creating a novel interaction network structure, distinct from native plant-fungal interactions. Finally, I will briefly present recent findings using environmental DNA to examine how fungal communities respond to gradients of land-use intensification, including indigenous forest, pine plantations, grasslands, and vineyards which suggests quite distinct response patterns of fungal communities compared to other biota (e.g., bacteria, animals, plants). Preliminary evidence suggests that at least some of these changes, too, are linked closely to plant-fungal interaction networks. Taken as a whole, each study helps contribute to our understanding of the unique fungal communities of New Zealand and how these communities are responding to changing soil environments.

Presented 16 October 2015

Extending the vertical perspective on Earth's skin – soils within the Critical Zone framework: Andre Eger [Landcare Research]

The Critical Zone (CZ) is defined as the envelope between canopy and groundwater that is the basis for almost all terrestrial life on Earth. Understanding this space, “where rock meets life”, – its fundamental processes, its response to human interference and global/regional change – should therefore be of highest priority. At the intersection between rock, water, life and atmosphere, the processes here are driven by a network of physical, chemical and biological system components that are interconnected through myriad processes and feedbacks exchanging and transforming matter and energy. It was recognised less than a decade ago that further progress in our understanding of the behaviour of this truly critical zone will require a multidisciplinary framework. As a result, Critical Zone Observatories (CZOs) were introduced. A CZO is a discrete study site of variable size, often a catchment, where a multitude of CZ-processes are monitored and studied by a multidisciplinary team with the aim to understand and quantify the processes within the CZ and the CZ's response to environmental change and/or human impact. Currently, CZOs mainly exist as part of national (USA) and multinational (European Union) networks of observatories. However, by recognising the limitations of existing sites in studying the full breadth of Earth's environmental conditions, efforts have begun to further internationalise the CZOs by creating an international network, which explicitly strives to include sites in the Southern Hemisphere. Using the example of the Western Southern Alps I will illustrate some aspects of the complexity of CZO processes. I will show a preliminary data set that “digs deeper” and explores the chemical processes that operate in different parts of the CZ, namely soil and bedrock. The data comes from the chemical analysis of various water sources, soil and bedrock samples collected in the Hokitika catchment, an environment which is annually exposed to 10 m of rain and 10 mm tectonic uplift. By using phosphorus as an example, the data indicate a chemically very structured CZ, where intensive chemical alteration and depletion of elements is not restricted to the soil only. Moreover, two very different weathering processes, carbonate and silicate weathering, seem to operate in different parts of the catchment. Luckily for a scientist, the results pose more questions than they give answers. Addressing them satisfactorily will require a multidisciplinary effort that draws from pedology, geology, hydrology, biogeochemistry and ecology.

Presented 9 October 2015

Ericoid root symbioses and soil carbon cycling: Gwen Grelet [Landcare Research]

Ericoid root symbioses are mutualistic plant-fungal associations restricted to the Ericaceae plant family. As such they are the type of root symbioses that have attracted the least attention, and are still poorly understood. Yet ericoid mycorrhizal plants occur worldwide. The ecosystems in which they occur abundantly hold over 1/5th of the world's soil C stock. The fungal partners involved in these symbiotic interactions appear to be highly interactive with soil organic matter, compared to other types of mycorrhizal fungi. I will use physiological, isotopic and molecular data to illustrate how these fungi interact with soil carbon cycling directly or through their hosts. I will then present newly emerging genomics data to demonstrate that ericoid fungi are equipped with a genetic attire underpinning highly aggressive and diverse carbohydrate degrading capabilities. These findings suggest ERM fungi might be key players in determining the fate of soil C under changing environmental conditions. However we are still far from being able to fully describe and quantify the impact of ERM fungi on soil C, and consequences on carbon balance of ERM-rich ecosystems. Several unresolved issues will need to be addressed first: How are ERM decomposing abilities regulated, particularly by plant versus soil carbon or nutrients? Would changes to and within ericoid mycorrhizal community yield significant impact on soil carbon? I will finish my talk by briefly exploring these questions using conceptual and preliminary experimental data.

Presented 23 October 2015

Mobilisation of selenium on the South Island West Coast: David Hawke [CPIT]

Until recent augmentation by the importation of fortified Australian wheat, the selenium status of New Zealanders has been comparatively low. In prehistoric times, the abundant seabirds that bred across the landscape would have provided a substantial external selenium source, conveyed through seabird colony soil processes. In this talk we will show that the external selenium provided by seabirds in the highly leached soils of the West Coast has little effect on levels of selenium in plants or in stream biota. Furthermore, stoichiometric analysis suggests that the ecosystem as a whole actively excludes this marine selenium relative to nitrogen and phosphorus uptake. We suggest that selenium uptake dynamics on the West Coast are a mixture of redox, adsorption and mycorrhizal processes.

Presented 25 September 2015

Options to reduce nitrate leaching losses from agricultural soils: Brendon Malcolm [Plant & Food Research]

Nitrate leaching losses from livestock systems is an increasing environmental concern, driven largely by the greater numbers of animals farmed through land-use intensification. Most losses occur during winter when soils are often draining and there is minimal growth/N uptake by plants. Therefore, better use of soil N during winter will inevitably result in reduced leaching losses. This presentation will outline recent research work that has identified possible approaches to reduce nitrate leaching losses from soils through the strategic use of pastoral plants.

Presented 30 October 2015

Evaluating soil oxygen as determining factor in nitrous oxide emissions:

Jen Owens [AGLS Lincoln University]

To enhance the quality and quantity of milk production, many dairy operations in New Zealand are using irrigation to improve pasture quality and yield. Nitrous oxide (N₂O) is a potent greenhouse gas, and urine patches from ruminant animals, such as cows, are a significant source of N₂O emissions. Despite the widespread use of irrigation on grazed pastures, few studies have examined how N₂O emissions from urine patches may be affected by irrigation practices. Soil moisture differences due to different irrigation scheduling may influence supply and demand of soil oxygen (O₂). This in turn may influence nitrous oxide reductase enzymes, which are responsible for reducing N₂O to di-nitrogen (N₂). Despite the importance of soil O₂ to biological N₂O and N₂ production, it is rarely measured. The objective of this study was to test whether irrigation frequency influenced N₂O emissions from urine patches on a free draining grazed pasture soil. Urine and non-urine treated soils were subjected to either a three day or six day irrigation regime. Daily N₂O fluxes were measured in situ along with other environmental and soil variables, including soil O₂. Denitrification enzyme assays were performed over time to assess the potential N₂O/(N₂O+N₂) ratio. Urine increased N₂O emissions but irrigation frequency did not have an effect. However, both urine and irrigation frequency treatments significantly affected soil moisture, and the influence of these treatments on soil O₂ varied with soil depth. This research contributes to our understanding of the net effects of irrigation practices, and has scientific and land management implications.

Presented 18 September 2015

Earthworm contribution to ecosystem services: Nicole Schon [AgResearch]

We all benefit from the services ecosystems provide. Soils and the organisms living in the soil play an integral role in the provision of these services. The two main drivers by which earthworms contribute to the processes that support ecosystem services is through 1) their feeding on organic matter to increase soil formation and nutrient availability, and 2) their burrowing activity to increase aggregate building and soil porosity and water and air movement. In this presentation we take a look at the contribution earthworms make to the provision of services and also explore how this contribution is influenced by earthworm functional diversity. Services examined include the provisioning of food as well as the regulating services including the recycling of wastes, carbon storage, regulation of nitrous oxide and the regulation of pests and disease.

Presented 13 November 2015

Supporting sustainable intensification of the New Zealand forestry industry: Simeon Smail [SCION]

To attain productivity goals, the New Zealand forestry sector is examining options to intensify the management of the planted estate. Many of these options, such as increased organic matter removal and fertiliser use, have the potential to significantly degrade soil nutrient pools and the soils processes that support plant growth. Through the “Growing confidence in forestry’s future” research programme Scion is working with industry to develop management plans that will increase site productivity without compromising the contribution of the soil to current and future rotations. Scion is also actively engaged in research to use the soil itself as a driver of greater productivity through improved understanding of plant-soil-microbe interactions, improving our ability to effectively utilise plant growth promoting activity.

Presented 2 October 2015

Soils: a key reservoir of life on Earth - what we know and don't know: Steve Wakelin [AgResearch]

Soils are the 'engine room' of agricultural production. Understanding the microbiology within soil is fundamental towards goals of achieving increased productivity and sustainability of agricultural systems, and also for understanding the mechanistic basis of the multitude of soil ecological functions that support human wellbeing. However our attempts to harness the potential of soil microbiology towards achieving such gains is often thwarted by three intrinsic factors: scale, diversity, and complexity. New approaches, based on ecosystem theory and ecological genomics, offer a new opportunity to understand and manage soil microbiology for gains in farm profitability and environmental sustainability.

Presented 11 September 2015

Soil acidity and aluminium toxicity in New Zealand soils: Amy Whitley [Lincoln University]

Soil acidity is an increasing issue globally affecting agricultural soils. An estimated 30% of the world's soils are acidic and below a soil pH of 5.5, while 75% of these soils suffer from subsoil acidity. The acidification of soils is caused by a combination of natural and anthropogenic processes over time. Soil acidity and associated aluminium (Al) toxicity severely limit the establishment, growth and persistence of legumes in New Zealand hill and high country soils. Legumes play a critical role in these grazed pasture systems, providing a high quality feed source for stock and critically fix atmospheric N (N₂). Many pasture legumes are sensitive to acid soils and aluminium toxicity which reduce the yield and persistence of these legumes. However, it is often uneconomic for farmers to apply lime across extensive hill and high country areas with challenging topography. The first step in the remediation process is to identify which soils are most susceptible to Al toxicity and the key drivers of Al variability in soils. This research aims to improve the understanding of Al concentrations in NZ high country soils. This presentation will provide a background to soil acidity and aluminium toxicity, as well as highlight current research which is being conducted on soil pH and aluminium toxicity at Lincoln University.

Presented 6 November 2015